

Appendix 1. Conceptual definitions and key features of workplace violence and related constructs ($n = 53$).

Concept and Organisation	Definition	Components	Targets	Perpetrators	Intent/ Power Use	Gender Sensitivity	References
WPV							
British Health and Safety Executive (1996)	An incident where an employee is threatened or assaulted by a member of the public during work	P, PSY	Worker	Non-worker	Unclear	Low	Haleem & Bingawi (2024)
European Commission (2001)	Worker offended, threatened, or attacked, endangering safety or well-being	P, PSY	Worker	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Haleem & Bingawi (2024)
ICN (2017)	Any work-related incident where a staff member is abused, threatened, or assaulted	P, PSY	Worker	Unspecified	Explicit/ Implicit	Low	Zhao et al., 2025
ILO (2016)	Behaviour departing from reasonable conduct, resulting in assault, threat, harm, or injury at or due to work.	P, PSY	Worker (implicit)	Unclear	Unclear	Low	López-Ros et al. (2023); Pagnucci et al. (2022)
ILO (2019)	Unacceptable behaviours or causing physical, sexual, or economic harm, including GBVH	P, S, E	Worker	Unclear	Unclear	High	Recla-Vamenta et al. (2023)
ILO (2021)	Verbal harassment, threats, or abuse at work that endangers safety, health, and well-being	P, PSY	Worker	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Tuominen et al. (2023)
ILO, International Council of Nurses [ICN], & Public Services International [PSI] (2002)	Intentional use of physical force or power against oneself, another, or a group, likely to cause harm or deprivation	P, PSY	Self, others, groups	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Somani et al. (2021)
NIOSH (2014)	Acts or threats of violence, from verbal abuse to physical assaults, directed at workers on duty	P, PSY	Worker	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Aljohani (2021); Martinez & Oliveira (2021); Odes et al. (2021); Zhao et al., 2025
Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority (2012)	Incidents where an employee is abused, sexually harassed, or assaulted at work	P, PSY, S	Worker	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Haleem & Bingawi (2024)
US-OSHA (2019)	Use or threat of physical force in the workplace, causing or likely to cause injury.	P	Worker	Unclear	Explicit	Low	López-Ros et al. (2023); Somani et al. (2021)
US-OSHA (n.d.)	Act or threat of violence, harassment, intimidation, or disruptive behaviour at work	P, PSY, H	Worker (implicit)	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Balis et al. (2025); Fricke et al. (2023); Hallett et al. (2023); Odes et al. (2021); Spencer et al. (2023); Zhao et al. (2025)
WHO (2002)	Intentional use of force or power against oneself, others, or groups, likely to result in harm	P, PSY	Self, others, groups	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Ajuwa et al. (2024); Civilotti et al. (2021); Munday et al. (2023); Somani et al. (2021)
WHO, ILO, ICN, & PSI Joint Programme (2003)	Incidents where staff are abused, threatened, or assaulted during work or commuting, challenging safety or health	P, PSY	Worker	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Alhomoud (2025); Aljohani (2021); Ayaz et al. (2024); Ayasreh & Hayajneh (2021); Dafny et al.

Concept and Organisation	Definition	Components	Targets	Perpetrators	Intent/ Power Use	Gender Sensitivity	References
---	Include, but is not limited to, harassment, incivility, gossiping, backbiting, persistent criticism, verbal and physical attacks, bullying, and mobbing	P, PSY, S, H	Unclear	Unclear	Explicit/ Implicit/	Low	(2024); Feruglio et al. (2024); Huang et al. (2022); Jang et al. (2022b); Kumari, Sarkar et al. (2022); Nelson et al. (2024); Varghese et al. (2022); Wang et al. (2022); Zhang et al. (2021) Parsons et al. (2021)
Aggression							
American Psychological Association [APA] (2020)	Behaviour intended to harm others physically or psychologically	P, PSY	Unclear	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Amara & Hansen (2024); Odes et al. (2021)
---	Including sexual attacks	P, PSY, S	Worker	Patients and visitors	Explicit	Low	Zhao et al. (2025)
GBVH							
ILO (2019)	Violence and harassment directed at persons due to sex or gender, or disproportionately affecting one gender.	H	Unclear	Unclear	Implicit	High	Ayaz et al. (2024)
UN-CEDAW (1992)	Violence against women because of their gender or disproportionately affecting one gender	Unclear	Women	Unclear	Implicit	High	Nelson et al. (2024)
Patient aggression and violence							
--	Violence and aggression encountered by physicians from patients or their relatives/friends	General violence	Physicians	Patients, their relatives/friends	Unclear	Low	Wu et al. (2024)
Occupational violence							
Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety (2019)	Abuse, threats, intimidation, or assault occurring during work	P, PSY	Worker (implicit)	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Provost et al. (2021)
Victorian Department of Health and Human Services (2017)	Abuse, threats, or assaults in work-related circumstances	P, PSY	Worker (implicit)	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Grant et al. (2022)
Violence against healthcare workers							

Concept and Organisation	Definition	Components	Targets	Perpetrators	Intent/ Power Use	Gender Sensitivity	References
--	Verbal or behavioural threats, physical and sexual assaults, and cyberbullying by patients and/or visitors	P, PSY, S, H	Worker	Patients Visitors	Unclear	Low	Hou et al. (2023)
Bullying and related terms							
--	Repeated, intentional, and enduring negative behaviours at work, causing harm or domination (including harassment, intimidation, exclusion, isolation, hostility, criticism)	P, PSY	Coworkers	Coworkers	Explicit	Low	Cao et al. (2025); Galanis et al. (2024); Jang et al. (2022a); Jeong et al. (2024); Karatuna et al. (2020); Luca et al. (2024); Machul et al. (2024); Ribeiro & Sani (2024); Shorey & Wong (2021); Woon (2023); Yang et al. (2024); Yosep et al. (2024); Zhang et al. (2025); Zhou et al. (2024)
Aul (2017) and Dellasega (2009), accepted by the American Nurses Association [ANA] (horizontal violence)	Lateral or peer harassment, verbal or non-verbal, within hierarchical or peer relations	PSY, H	Coworkers	Coworkers	Unclear	Low	Fernández-Gutiérrez & Mosteiro-Díaz (2021)
(upwards violence)	Disruptive, aggressive, or hostile behaviours among coworkers of the same hierarchical level	PSY	Coworkers	Coworkers	Unclear	Low	Luca et al. (2024); Reguera-Carrasco et al. (2025); Zhang, Cai et al. (2022); Zhang, Yin et al. (2022)
(mobbing)	negative behaviour directed by subordinates (e.g., nursing staff, students, or faculty) toward nurse leaders who are in a position of authority over them Repeated, systematic hostile acts causing personal damage over time	PSY	Superior coworkers	Subordinate coworkers	Unclear	Low	Parsons et al. (2021)
			Worker	Unclear	Explicit	Low	Fernández-Gutiérrez & Mosteiro-Díaz (2021); Jang et al. (2022a); Recla-Vamenta et al. (2023); Reguera-Carrasco et al. (2025); Ribeiro & Sani (2024)
Incivility							
ANA (2021)	Rude or disrespectful speech or actions that may lack clear intent but cause interpersonal harm	P, PSY	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Cao et al. (2025); Luca et al. (2024); Ribeiro & Sani (2024)
Sexual harassment							
---	Unwanted verbal, gestural, or physical acts of a sexual nature that violate dignity or create an offensive environment	P, PSY, H	Unclear	Unclear	Explicit	High	Mohammed et al. (2024); Smith et al. (2022)

Concept and Organisation	Definition	Components	Targets	Perpetrators	Intent/ Power Use	Gender Sensitivity	References
---	Unwelcome and inappropriate propositioning or gifts, sexual attention or overtones, exposed genitals, suggestive looks, sexual jokes or stories, or requests for physical examinations	P, PSY, S, H	Unclear	Unclear	Explicit	High	Parsons et al. (2021); Woon (2023)

Legend: P = Physical; PSY = Psychological; S = Sexual; H = Harassment; E = Economic.

Appendix 2. Theoretical frameworks on GBVH in the included studies ($n = 57$).

Level of Analysis	Description	Contextual Variables	Source(s)
Individual/Psychological			
Affective-Predatory Violence Model (McEllistrem, 2004)	Distinguishes emotionally reactive, impulsive violence from premeditated, goal-directed violence, aiding clinical violence assessment	I, A, C	Hou et al. (2023)
Attachment Theory	Defines stalking as a maladaptive behaviour stemming from incompetence and emotional isolation	I	Harris et al. (2023)
Cognitive Model of Patient Aggression	Examines cognitive processes underlying aggression	A	Haleem & Bingawi (2024)
Psychological Capital (Luthans et al., 2007)	Defines self-efficacy, optimism, resilience, and hope as key personal resources protecting against stress and burnout in the workplace	R	Machul et al. (2024)
Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow)	Workplace safety is a basic need essential for psychological well-being	A	Zhang et al. (2021)
Self-Efficacy and Locus of Control Theory (Dunn et al., 2007)	Training enhances confidence and internal control in violent workplace situations	R	Dafny et al. (2024)
Transactional Stress/Coping Theory (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984)	Coping involves ongoing appraisal and adjustment, with strategies focused on emotions and problems	R, A, C	Önal et al. (2023); Ribeiro & Sani (2024)
Conservation of Resources (CoR) Theory (Hobfoll, 2001)	Social, task, and personal resources mediate stress, and resource gains or losses shape adaptation and resilience in WPV contexts	R, A, C	Odes et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2022)
Good Lives Model (GLM; Ward & Gannon, 2006)	Advocates for strength-based risk management in forensic mental health settings, emphasising collaborative prevention planning	P, U	Luigi et al. (2024)
Resilience Theory (Angst, 2009)	Repeated procedural coping enables adaptation to chronic violence stressors.	R	Ribeiro & Sani (2024)
Novice-to-Expert Model (Benner, 1982)	Describes five progressive stages (novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert) by which nurses develop clinical skill and judgment through education and practical experience	P, R	Alshawush et al. (2022)
Transition Theory (Duchscher, 2008)	Examines psychological and social challenges that new graduates encounter during their role transition to practice, especially regarding exposure to WPV	P, R	Alshawush et al. (2022)
Interpersonal/Relational			
Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977)	Explains how observing and modelling senior nurses' negative behaviour leads junior nurses to adopt it, perpetuating horizontal WPV and bullying during socialisation	A, U	Zhang et al. (2025)
Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964)	Explores reciprocity and power dynamics in WPV, particularly in horizontal violence and nurse turnover	I, U	Odes et al. (2021)
Social Identity Theory (Turner et al., 1979)	Identifies group boundary enforcement and in-group/out-group dynamics as drivers of bullying and violence in nursing	A, U	Zhang et al. (2025)
Interpersonal Relations Theory (Peplau, 1952)	Focuses on therapeutic nurse-patient relationships to reduce violence in mental health settings	A, P, U	Amara & Hansen (2024)

Grounded Theory of Nurse Bullying	Provides an empirically validated framework for understanding bullying dynamics among emergency nurses	A, U	Machul et al. (2024)
Stalking Coping Methods Framework	Organises stalking responses into five domains: engagement, resistance, avoidance, empowerment, and external support	R	Harris et al. (2023)
Violence Against ED Nurses Model (Hou et al., 2022)	Role reversal of assailants (patients/visitors) and victims (nurses) influenced by crowding and attacker traits	A	Hou et al. 2023
Influential Work (Lawler, 1991)	Explores nursing students' experiences with professional norms and relational dynamics affecting WPV	A	Smith et al. (2022)
Organisational/Structural			
U.S. Department of Justice/NIOSH Typology (2001)	Classifies WPV by perpetrators: Type I (criminal intent), Type II (patient/family/ visitor), Type III (worker-on-worker), and Type IV (personal/domestic spillover)	I, A, C	Ayaz et al. (2024); Civilotti et al. (2021); Clari et al. (2020); Kim & Lee (2024); Lu et al. (2024); Odes et al. (2021); Pompeii et al. (2020); Small et al. (2020); Somani et al. (2021); Travaini et al. (2024)
VA/DoD Framework (Brewin et al., 2000)	Categorises trauma risk factors as pre-, peri-, and post-event influences on violence exposure and recovery	A, C	Hilton et al. (2022); Hou et al. (2023)
Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007)	The balance between job demands (e.g., verbal aggression) and resources (e.g., support) in determining vulnerability to burnout and WPV	A, C, U	Pariona-Cabrera et al. (2020); Wang et al. (2022)
Person-Environment Fit Theory (Kelly et al., 2015)	Poor fit between environments and individuals increases stress and WPV vulnerability	A, U	Odes et al. (2021)
Human Factors Framework	Highlights the role of workload and patient/family complaints in WPV incidence	U	Machul et al. (2024)
Model for Healthy Work Environments (Registered Nurses' Association of Ontario)	Defines workplace factors, policies, and relationships that support safety and reduce violence among nurses	P, U	Fricke et al. (2023)
Quality Caring Model (Duffy)	Positions caring practices as essential organisational values to enhance staff safety and minimise WPV in healthcare.	P, U	Dafny et al. (2024)
Bureaucratic Caring Theory (Ray, 1989)	Links the administrative structure and nursing leadership with effective interventions against workplace bullying	P, U	Luca et al. (2024)
Donabedian Model (1988)	Organises quality indicators for WPV interventions into three domains: structure (e.g., staffing, environment), process (e.g., care practices), and outcomes (e.g., adverse events, perceptions), to support organisational evaluation and improvement	P, U	Lyver et al. (2024); Machul et al. (2024)
Theories of Organisational Justice (Adams, Greenberg)	Investigates fairness perception as a mediator of WPV and workplace bullying	A, U	Xu et al. (2025)
Power-Dependence Relations (Emerson)	Examines power imbalances in Intensive Care Unit settings as contributors to workplace mistreatment	U	Zhang et al. (2025)
Three "I" Model (Stacey et al., 2015)	Promotes risk management through informed, involved, and influential decision-making	P, U	Luigi et al. (2024)

Levels of Prevention (Primary, Secondary, Tertiary)	Classifies WPV interventions as primary (prevention), secondary (early intervention), and tertiary (mitigation of long-term effects)	P	Jang et al. (2022a); Small et al. (2020)
Clinical Confidence (Thackery, 1987)	Evaluates improvements in staff competence and confidence resulting from WPV interventions	P, R	Dafny et al. (2024)
General Learning Theories	Broad theories underpinning educational programme design in aggression management and WPV prevention training	P, R	Dafny et al. (2024)
Development of Knowledge and Competence Theories (Arends 2006, Arnold & Siebert 1999; Petersen 2000)	Underpins aggression management programmes with adult learning and professional competence theory	P, R, U	Dafny et al. (2024)
Kirkpatrick Evaluation Model (1967)	Assess WPV programme effectiveness across four levels: participant reaction, knowledge/skill acquisition, workplace behaviour change, and organisational results.	P, R	Dafny et al., 2024; Johnston & Fox (2020); Martinez & Oliveira (2021)
Transition to Practice Model (National Council of State Boards of Nursing, 2015)	Guides transition programmes that support new nursing graduates in facing workplace challenges, including WPV	P, R	Alshawush et al. (2022)
Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1993)	Supports training interventions that strengthen self-efficacy and coping skills for aggression management	P, R	Dafny et al. (2024)
Sociocultural			
ILO/ICN/WHO/PSI WPV Framework (2002)	Provides an internationally endorsed blueprint for gender-sensitive prevention, training, and policy against healthcare violence	P, U	Nelson et al. (2024); Somani et al. (2021)
Power-Threat Model (McLaughlin et al., 2012) and Hierarchy of Power Model (Jack et al., 2021)	Gender and status-based risks; hierarchy increases bullying/harassment	A, U	Smith et al. (2022); Yosep et al. (2024)
Minority Stress and Intersectional Identities Theories	Explains violence vulnerabilities in minority populations	A, U	Lyver et al. (2024)
Gender-Based WPV	Recognises violence as rooted in socio-economic, cultural, and gendered factors, supporting gender-sensitive intervention approaches	A, P, U	Nelson et al. (2024)
Oppression Theory (Freire, 1972) and Structural Violence Theory (Farmer et al., 2006)	Systemic power imbalances and discrimination drive violence	A, U	Reguera-Carrasco et al. (2025)
GLOBE Study (House et al., 2004)	Cross-national framework on culture (power distance, assertiveness, collectivism, and performance orientation) shaping WPV perceptions and responses, especially in healthcare	A, P, R, U	Karatuna et al. (2020)
Cultural Dimensions (Hofstede, 1984)	Contrasts how values such as collectivism-individualism and hierarchy-egalitarianism affect WPV patterns and tolerance	A, U	Xu et al. (2025)
Gender Mainstreaming	Integrates gender-focused approaches in WPV interventions		Nelson et al. (2024)
Integrative/Multilevel			
Socioecological Model (SEM; CDC, 2022)	Explains WPV via interlinked levels: individual (e.g., age, gender), relationships (e.g., workplace	U	Kim & Lee (2024)

	interactions), community (e.g., organisation protocols), and societal (e.g., laws, policies).		
Multifactorial Conceptual Model (Cooper & Swanson, 2002)	Details complex interactions among workers, aggressors, and organisational contexts	I, A, C, U	Civilotti et al. (2021); Dafny et al. (2024); Fricke et al. (2023)
Complexity Theory (Flannery & Flannery, 2023)	Dynamic reciprocal interactions among environmental, staff, patient, and organisational factors	A, U	Amara & Hansen (2024)
Integrated Healthcare WPV Model (Bhattacharjee, 2021)	Prevention balances organisational/societal (distal) and individual factors (proximal)	A, P, U	Wu et al. (2024)
WPV Contextual Risk Assessment Framework	A contextual risk assessment framework for healthcare organisations evaluates WPV risk by systematically analysing patient/visitor, staff, environment, organisational policy, and socio-cultural factors.	A, U	Jeong et al. (2024); Lyver et al. (2024); O'Brien et al. (2024)
Multicomponent Prevention Models	Integrate staff training, policy reforms, and violence management strategies for comprehensive WPV prevention.	P, U	López-Ros et al. (2023)
SafeWards Model (Bowers, 2014)	A psychiatric care framework that links staff actions with reduced violence and coercion	P, U	Doedens et al. (2025); Johnston & Fox, (2020); López-Ros et al. (2023); Wu et al. (2024)
Capacity, Opportunity, Motivation, Behaviour (COM-B) Framework (Hinsby & Baker, 2004)	Focuses on capacity, opportunity, and motivation as determinants of behaviour change in WPV prevention training	P, R, U	Amara & Hansen (2024); Xie et al. (2025)
Supporting Formal Theories	Uses psychological theories (e.g., self-efficacy, learning risk) as foundations for educational strategies aimed at preventing WPV	P, U	Provost et al. (2021);
Organisational and Personal Factors	Classifies WPV as organisational (e.g., policy, leadership) or personal (e.g., demographic, coping), emphasising multifaceted vulnerability	A, R, U	Lozano et al. (2021)

Note: A = antecedents; C = consequences; I = intentionality; P = prevention or mitigation; R = personal resources; U = upstream variables.

Appendix 3. Summary of assessment tools of WPV in healthcare ($n = 24$).

Instrument	Main purpose and dimensions assessed	Population/Context	Psychometric properties	Scope	Limitations	Source
WPV Exposure and Surveillance						
Workplace Violence in the Health Sector Survey Questionnaire (WHO/ILO/ICN/PSI)	Assesses physical, verbal, psychological, and sexual violence; identifies perpetrators, frequency, reporting mechanisms, and organisational responses	All healthcare workers; cross-cultural	$\alpha > .80$; validated internally in > 20 languages	Standardised and cross-culturally validated instrument suitable for surveillance and policy	Cultural adaptation needed; variable recall periods (12 months vs lifetime)	López-Ros et al. (2023); Lu et al. (2024); Matta et al. (2024); Rehan et al. (2023); Zhang et al. (2021)
Workplace Violence Questionnaire/Scale	Quantifies exposure to physical, verbal, and sexual violence	Healthcare staff	$\alpha > .85$; validated across regions	Enables regional comparison	Inconsistent terminology and recall reduce comparability	Berger et al. (2024); Galanis et al. (2024); Fatai et al. (2025); Lozano et al. (2021); Matta et al. (2024); Varghese et al. (2022)
Survey of Violence Experienced by Staff (SOVES)	Documents exposure, perpetrator, type and impact of violence	Psychiatric, emergency departments	$\alpha \approx .83$; validated in Europe and North America	Captures incident characteristics and organisational responses	Limited global use; older validation base	Berger et al. (2024); Hilton et al. (2022); Wang et al. (2022)
Violent Incident Form (VIF)	Records and categorises violent episodes for reporting	Healthcare staff	Not reported	Facilitates standardised reporting for audits and prevention	Focused on event reporting only; limited global use	Civilotti et al. (2021); Galanis et al. (2024)
Bullying, Incivility, and Negative Acts						
Negative Acts Questionnaire–Revised (NAQ-R)	Measures bullying and negative interpersonal acts without explicit <i>violence</i> labeling	Nurses, multidisciplinary healthcare staff	$\alpha > .80$; strong cross-cultural validity	Widely used; minimises bias; captures peer/organisational aggression	Focused on psychological WPV only; varied cut-offs	Fricke et al. (2023); Galanis et al. (2024); Jang et al. (2022a); Jeong et al. (2024); Lozano et al. (2021); Reguera-Carrasco et al. (2025)
Nursing Incivility Scale (NIS)	Evaluates interpersonal incivility across eight subscales (e.g., gossip, disrespect)	Nurses	$\alpha \approx .76$ –.83	Sensitive to intra-professional hostility	Nursing-specific; limited cross-occupational use	Berger et al. (2024); Galanis et al. (2024); Jang et al. (2022a)
Workplace Incivility Scale (WIS)	Measures incivility	Healthcare staff	$\alpha \approx .85$ –.86	Measures incivility from both supervisors and coworkers	Self-report bias	Lozano et al. (2021); Jang et al. (2022a)
Workplace Bullying Inventory	Not reported	Not reported (assume nurses)	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	Jeong et al. (2024)

Instrument	Main purpose and dimensions assessed	Population/ Context	Psychometric properties	Scope	Limitations	Source
Lateral and Vertical Violence in Nursing Survey	Measures lateral and vertical violence, including associated factors such as contributing factors, frequency, seriousness, and fear of retaliation	Nurses	Not reported	Used to assess nurse-to-nurse conflict and disruptive behaviors among colleagues of the same hierarchical level (lateral violence) and conflicts involving different hierarchical levels (vertical violence)	Lack of standardization; self-report bias	Jang et al. (2022a)
Verbal Abuse Questionnaire (VAQ)	Measures verbal abuse	Healthcare staff	Not reported	Quantifies exposure to verbal abuse	Self-report bias	Mohammed et al. (2024)
Student Experience of Bullying during Clinical Placement	Measures bullying, verbal abuse, physical violence, racial harassment, and sexual harassment during clinical practice	Nursing students				Mohammed et al. (2024);
Patient or Visitor Aggression Toward Healthcare Staff						
Hospital Aggressive Behaviour Scale–Users (HABS-U)	Captures the type, frequency, and severity of patient and visitor aggression	Hospital staff	$\alpha > .80$; convergent validity supported	Context-specific; complements general tools	Limited to acute hospitals; new scale	Berger et al. (2024); Matta et al. (2024); Lozano et al. (2021)
Perception of Prevalence Aggression Scale (POPAS)	Measures staff perceptions, attitudes, and thresholds for defining aggression	Psychiatric, emergency, and high-risk units	Not reported	Addresses cognitive and attitudinal aspects of WPV	Outdated validation; potential cultural bias	Hilton et al. (2022); Kumari, Sarkar et al. (2022); Wang et al. (2022)
Confidence in Coping with Patient Aggression Instrument (CCPAI)	Assesses staff confidence and coping strategies; 10-item questionnaire	Mental health and acute care staff	$\alpha = .78-.88$; construct validity supported	Evaluates training and preparedness	Not a prevalence tool; self-efficacy focus	Dafny et al. (2024); Kumari, Sarkar et al. (2022); Munday et al. (2023)
De-escalating Aggressive Behaviour Scale (DABS)	Measures de-escalation skill proficiency and behavioural responses	Nurses, mental health professionals	$\alpha \approx .80-.87$; factor validity confirmed	Useful for training and intervention studies	Narrow scope; not suited for prevalence research	Doedens et al. (2025) Dafny et al. (2024)
Brøset Violence Checklist (BVC)	Assesses/predicts the risk of imminent violence within 24 hours	Inpatients	AUC $\approx .85-.93$ (high level of accuracy)	Used in acute care mental health settings and forensic psychiatric hospitals	Limited generalizability to non-psychiatric settings	Berger et al. (2024); Fricke et al. (2023)
Violence Risk Screening-10 (V-RISK-10)	Violence risk prediction	Inpatients	AUC $\approx .82-.84$ (high level of accuracy)	Used in acute care mental health settings	Limited generalizability to non-mental health settings	Fricke et al. (2023)

Instrument	Main purpose and dimensions assessed	Population/ Context	Psychometric properties	Scope	Limitations	Source
Dynamic Appraisal of Situational Aggression (DASA)	Risk assessment	Inpatients	AUC \approx .83 (high level of accuracy)	Used in acute care mental health settings and forensic psychiatric hospitals	Non-standardisation; Setting specificity	Fricke et al. (2023)
Reporting, Incident Documentation, and Organisational Response						
Workplace Violence Safety Climate (WVSC)	Assesses employer safety strategies intended to decrease WPV incidents in the home care setting	Home Healthcare staff	$\alpha \approx$.86	Overall assessment of home visit safety, providing necessary risk information that can be shared among staff	Setting specificity	Small et al. (2020)
Protection Matrix Risk Assessment and Management	Assess home visiting risk prior to the first visit by healthcare worker	Home Healthcare staff	Not reported	Risk assessment of home settings for home visiting, coded in low, moderate and high risk	Setting specificity	Small et al. (2020)
Home Visit Risk Scale	Assesses risks associated with violence in home care	Home healthcare staff	$\alpha \approx$.77	Assists home healthcare workers in making effective safety decisions and providing essential risk information to other staff	Setting specificity; self-reported bias	Small et al. (2020)
Multilevel and Structural/Contextual Assessment						
Cultural Violence Scale	Measures discrimination and symbolic violence (ethnicity, religion, cultural identity)	Nurses in Middle Eastern and multicultural contexts	$\alpha \approx$.80; preliminary validation	Adds structural and cultural dimensions	Limited adoption; no cross-cultural testing	Shohani & Tavan (2024)
Coping and Response to WPV						
Ways of Coping Questionnaire/Checklist (WCCL)	Examines an individual's coping strategies in stressful situations	Healthcare staff	Not reported	Strategies are primarily categorised into two dimensions: Emotion-focused coping and Problem-focused coping.	Retrospective self-report	Ribeiro & Sani (2024)
Workplace Violence Safety Climate (WVSC)	Examines safety strategies adopted at work	Home Healthcare Staff	$\alpha \approx$.86	Evaluates what strategies are employed by workers regarding their safety at work	Setting specificity	Small et al. (2020)
Personal Safety Decision Scale (PSDS)	Assess decisions regarding own safety at work	Home Healthcare Staff	$\alpha \approx$.58	Evaluates decisions made by home healthcare workers regarding their safety at work	Setting specificity	Small et al. (2020)

Appendix 4. Implemented interventions, objectives, outcomes, and critical assessment ($n = 29$).

Specific Interventions	Targeted WPV Type(s)	Main Objectives	Evidence Summary	Sources
Policy, Administrative, and Organisational				
Zero-Tolerance Policies (e.g., OSHA, Joint Commission, Legislative action)	II; I-IV	Eliminate normalisation of violence and create shared commitment to a safe and respectful environment	Decreased violence incidence rates (e.g., 0.48 → 0.37); Greater staff safety culture and accountability; enhances civility; long term-culture shift required	Fricke et al. (2023); Berger et al. (2024); Haleem & Bingawi (2024); Lozano et al. (2021); Parsons et al. (2021); Spencer et al. (2023); Zhao et al. (2025)
Resource Allocation/Administrative Changes (e.g., staffing, waiting times, visiting hours)	I-IV	Foster culture of safety; reduce systemic stressors (understaffing, overcrowding)	Reduced patient frustration and potential incidents; diminished violence after evaluating system efficacy. Effective as a preventive measure, particularly by reducing waiting times (by 18.6%)	Alhomoud (2025); Fricke et al. (2023); Munday et al. (2023)
Culture of Civility and Trust Initiatives	III	Promote a culture of respect, civility, and psychological safety	Recommended as an organisational commitment to prevent incivility and support trust; quantitative data	Parsons et al. (2021)
Safety Prioritisation and Interdepartmental Collaboration	I-IV	Strengthen coordination and leadership commitment to staff safety	Qualitative evidence supports improved morale and prevention; part of broader cultural change	Zhao et al. (2025)
Environmental and Security				
Environmental Controls (e.g., Quiet Rooms, Surveillance, Object Removal)	I-II	Deter or delay aggression; ensure staff safety and incident containment; reduce triggers and opportunities for violence	Effective when combined with staff training and policy measures, it contributes to reduced aggression and perceived risk; shown to prevent escalation and ensure safety	Alhomoud (2025); Amara & Hansen (2024); Berger et al. (2024); Fricke et al. (2023); Haleem & Bingawi (2024); Woon (2023)
Assessment of Unmet Needs and Prevention Focus	II	Address root causes of agitation (pain, confusion, unmet needs)	Prevention perceived as more effective than reactive control	Woon (2023)
Physical Restraint (Last Resort)	II	Protect staff and patients when de-escalation fails	Ethical and safety considerations limit use; effective when unavoidable	Amara & Hansen (2024); Woon (2023)
Educational and Skills-Based				

Specific Interventions	Targeted WPV Type(s)	Main Objectives	Evidence Summary	Sources
Communication, Conflict Management and Decision-Making Training, Crisis Intervention Techniques, and Nonviolent Crisis Management Training	II; I-IV	Equip staff with skills to prevent escalation, respond effectively, and manage emotional impact	Increased self-efficacy, confidence, and coping ability; mixed evidence on reducing actual incident rates, resolving conflicts, and promoting empathy (win-win outcomes)	Alshawush et al. (2022); Amara & Hansen (2024); Fricke et al. (2023); Johnston & Fox (2020); Kumari, Sarkar et al. (2022); López-Ros et al. (2023); Martínez & Oliveira (2021); Parsons et al. (2021); Rija et al. (2022); Small et al. (2020); Somani et al. (2021); Tuominen et al. (2023); Yosep et al. (2023)
Assertiveness, Role Modeling, and Boundary-Setting Training and Team Building Exercises	III	Equip staff with de-escalation, crisis response, and emotional coping skills, while establishing nurse leaders and educators as assertive agents who model civility and professionalism	Improved staff self-efficacy, relationship management alongside effective bullying coping strategies, thereby reducing incivility, lateral violence, verbal abuse, and turnover, while establishing sustainable cultures of respect	Amara & Hansen (2024); Ayaz et al. (2024); Berger et al. (2024); Jeong et al. (2024); Luca et al. (2024); Munday et al. (2023); Parsons et al. (2021); Somani et al. (2021); Yosep et al. (2023)
Cognitive-Behavioural and Interpersonal Approaches (e.g., Promoting Adult Resilience [PAR]) and Resilience Building	III; I-IV	Improves cognitive appraisal, recognition, resilience and coping against WPV-related stress and interpersonal strain	Reduces stress symptoms, and improves self-regulation, mood stability, and relational skills among staff	Doedens et al. (2025); Zhao et al. (2025)
Cognitive Rehearsal (CR)	III	Enhances preparedness to respond to bullying or lateral aggression by practicing assertive communication	Reduces incivility and increases perceived control and professionalism in nursing teams	Jeon et al. (2024); Kumari, Sarkar et al. (2022); Martínez & Oliveira (2021)
De-Escalation with Dance Movement Therapy	II	Uses body-based and experiential strategies to build de-escalation and emotional regulation skills	Promotes embodied learning and improved patient interaction quality	Martínez & Oliveira (2021)
NIOSH Online WPV Prevention Course	I-IV	Provides interactive, scenario-based e-learning on WPV recognition, prevention, and response	Shown to improve knowledge retention and perceived preparedness	Johnston & Fox (2020); Martínez & Oliveira (2021)
Plus-Delta Simulation & Critical Incident Stress Debriefing	II-III	Provides reflective learning and stress management through feedback and group debriefing post-incident	Found to enhance coping, peer support, and emotional regulation within clinical teams	Dafny et al. (2024)
Trauma-Informed Approach	II-III	Integrates understanding of trauma's impact on both victims and perpetrators, shaping prevention and care	Enhances empathy, staff emotional safety, and recovery; improves the sustainability of prevention practices	Lyver et al. (2024)

Specific Interventions	Targeted WPV Type(s)	Main Objectives	Evidence Summary	Sources
Positive Behavioural Support (PBS)	II-III	Promotes coping and constructive management of aggressive or challenging behaviours	Shown to reduce reactive aggression and increase prosocial responses within teams	Doedens et al. (2025)
Realist Approach/CMO Configuration (Context-Mechanism-Outcome)	I-IV	Links context, mechanism, and outcome to explain how educational or organisational interventions work	Clarifies why certain WPV training succeeds or fails in specific hospital or emergency contexts	Provost et al. (2021)
Training Evaluation				
Theories of Learning Outcomes (Cognitive, Skill-Based, Affective)	I-IV	Guides the evaluation of training outcomes across cognitive, behavioural, and affective domains	Supports structured evaluation of educational WPV programmes	Dafny et al. (2024);
Reporting, Monitoring, and Accountability Systems				
Formal Incident Reporting Systems (paper or digital), Risk Monitoring Tools and Databases, Feedback and Learning Mechanisms	I-IV	Promote accountability, detect patterns, inform prevention, and empower staff to report safely	Increases awareness and reporting rates; remains underused due to fear of reprisal and inefficient systems	Xu et al. (2025); Haleem & Bingawi (2024); Munday et al. (2023); Somani et al. (2021); Tuominen et al. (2023); Wang et al. (2025)
Simplified and Reinforced Reporting Processes	I-IV	Increase incident reporting and organisational learning	Prevent normalisation and fosters responsiveness	Small et al. (2020); O'Brien et al., 2024; Zhao et al. (2025)
Psychological and Post-Incident Support Interventions				
Peer Support and Employee Assistance Programmes	I-IV	Mitigate trauma, reduce stress and burnout, improve coping and retention	Reduced symptoms of depression, anxiety, and traumatic stress; perceived as essential but under-implemented	Feruglio et al. (2024); Fricke et al. (2023); Johnston & Fox (2020); Yosep et al. (2023)
Counseling and Conflict Mediation for Perpetrators and Victims	II-III	Address root causes, promote empathy, and restore workplace relationships	Qualitative reports indicate improved resolution and trust	Parsons et al. (2021); Zhao et al. (2025)
Psychological Treatment Services for Affected Nurses	I-IV	Support recovery and retention post-incident	Improves coping and reduces turnover	Zhao et al. (2025)
User-Focused				

Specific Interventions	Targeted WPV Type(s)	Main Objectives	Evidence Summary	Sources
Patient/User Education (Awareness, Mutual Clarification of Rights and Duties, Collaborative Meetings, and Feedback Systems)	II	Reduce frustration, align expectations, and promote co-responsibility for safety	Reduced non-physical violence by 15–17%; strengthened user-staff relationships	López-Ros et al. (2023)
Role Modeling by Nurse Leaders	III	Model appropriate professional behaviours to discourage aggression	Perceived as highly effective in reducing bullying and improving student respect	Parsons et al. (2021)
Orientation and Faculty Development on Managing Upward Violence	III	Increase preparedness of nurse educators and managers to manage aggression	Recommended as standard inclusion in training curricula	Parsons et al. (2021)
Curriculum Inclusion (Respectful Relationships, and WPV Management)	III	Educate future nurses on WPV recognition and professional behaviour	Improves awareness and respectful conduct	Parsons et al. (2021)
Prevention-Focused Assessment of Unmet Needs	II	Identify and address patient needs early to prevent escalation	Prevention emphasised overreaction; perceived as central to ensuring patient and staff safety	Woon (2023)
Organisational Follow-Up and Feedback Loops	I-IV	Ensure that reports lead to action and accountability	Lack of feedback and ineffective reporting linked to continued underreporting and resignation as coping	Parsons et al. (2021); Zhao et al. (2025)

Note: I = Type I (criminal intent); II = Type II (patient/visitor); III = Type III (worker-on-worker); Type IV = (personal/domestic spillover).